

Brief Review: Nasal Drug Delivery System for Migraine Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Nasal drug delivery involves administering medications through the nose for either local or systemic effects. Nasal drug delivery system has been considered as potential administration route. The human nasal cavity's total volume about 16 to 19 ml and total surface area of about 160 cm². The range of particle size for nasal administration is 10–50 micrometers (µm). Nasal route prevents the enzymatic or acidic degradation of drug. Avoiding the hepatic first pass elimination. For nasal drug delivery various formulations such as nasal gels, nasal spray, nasal pumps, micro emulsion, suspensions, powders and thermoreversible mucoadhesive gel have been mentioned in this study. Intranasal drug delivery system is currently being used in treatments of migraine, smoking cessation, Acute pain relief, osteoporosis, nocturnal enuresis and vitamin-B12 deficiency. Other examples of therapeutic areas under development or with potential for nasal delivery include cancer therapy, epilepsy, antiemetics, rheumatoid arthritis and Strategies for improving nasal drug delivery system by Improving the nasal residence time and enhancing the nasal absorption. Lipophilic drugs are generally well absorbed from the nasal cavity and approaching 100% bioavailability. It offers non-invasiveness, self-administration, patient comfort, and reduce patient compliance. The nasal delivery seems to be a favorable way to circumvent the obstacles for blood-brain barrier (BBB) allowing the direct drug delivery in the bio phase

of central nervous system (CNS) active compounds. It has also been considered for the administration of vaccines. The trigeminal nerve (Cranial Nerve 5), which controls sensibility (touch, pain, and temperature) and reflexes (sneezing, nasal congestion), innervates the nasal cavity. A Migraine is a neurological or familial disorder characterized by recurrent headache that can cause severe pain (tremendous headache), nausea, vomiting and hypersensitivity to light, sound, sometimes smell and touch. Migraine is a the third most common disease worldwide characterized by current episodes of severe headaches.

Keywords: Nasal drug delivery system, formulations of nasal drug delivery system, treatment of migraine.

INTRODUCTION

Nasal drug delivery system

One of the most potential alternative routes for excellent systemic availability of drugs limited to I.V. administration is nasal route. Nasal drug delivery can be a promising method for drugs that are active in low doses. Nasal drug delivery involves administering medications through the nose for either local or systemic effects. Nasal route has been achieving better systematic bioavailability by compared to oral routes. It is due to larger surface area, porous endothelial membrane, high total blood flow, the avoidance of first-pass metabolism, and ready accessibility ⁽¹⁾.

Intranasal drug delivery enables dose reduction, rapid attainment of therapeutic blood levels, quicker onset of pharmacological activity, and fewer side effects. It offers non-invasiveness, self-administration, patient comfort, and reduce patient compliance. The nasal delivery seems to be a favorable way to circumvent the obstacles for blood-brain barrier (BBB) allowing the direct drug delivery in the bio phase of central nervous system (CNS) active compounds. It has also been considered for the administration of vaccines. The nasal cavity as a feasible site for the administration of much therapeutic agents. Intranasal drug delivery system is currently being used in treatments of migraine, smoking cessation, Acute pain relief, osteoporosis, nocturnal enuresis and vitamin-B12 deficiency. Other examples of therapeutic areas under development or with potential for nasal delivery include cancer therapy, epilepsy, antiemetics, rheumatoid arthritis and insulin dependent

diabetes. For nasal drug delivery various formulations such as nasal gels, nasal spray, nasal pumps, micro emulsion, suspensions, powders and thermoreversible mucoadhesive gel have been studied ⁽²⁾.

Migraine

A Migraine is a neurological disorder characterized by recurrent headache that can cause tremendous headache, nausea, vomiting and hypersensitivity to light, sound, sometimes smell and touch. It can be triggered by various factors, including stress, certain foods, changes in sleep pattern, menstrual cycle, emotional stress and hormonal changes ⁽³⁾. Migraine is one of the most prolonged, often neglected, wrongly diagnosed, and under-treated neurological conditions leading to years of disability affecting billions of people worldwide ⁽⁴⁾. Migraine is the third most common disease worldwide characterized by current episodes of severe headaches ⁽⁵⁾. Migraine long lasting from 4 to 72 hours if untreated. It is more common to women than to men ⁽¹⁾.

Pathophysiology

The exact pathophysiology of migraine remains incompletely understood, it is complex and involves multiple interconnected mechanisms in the brain and vascular system ⁽⁵⁾.

Based on the available clinical and imaging data, the hypothalamus plays a crucial role in the onset of a migraine attack and in the regulation of the intensity of the attack. The main steps involved in the pathophysiology of the migraine,

- Trigger
- Brain Overreaction
- Nerve Activation
- Chemical Release
- Pain and Other Symptoms

Trigeminovascular system activation involving the release of calcitonin-gene-related peptide (CGRP) is a neurotransmitter responsible for the pain (inflammatory tissue responses) ⁽⁶⁾.

Diagnosis

International Headache Society diagnostic criteria for migraine with or without aura. A thorough history and physical examination can help to confirm the diagnosis of migraine and rule out emergent condition. The mnemonic POUND is an evidence-based aid for migraine diagnosis

- ❖ Pulsatile quality of headache
- ❖ One-day duration (four to 72 hours)
- ❖ Unilateral location
- ❖ Nausea or vomiting
- ❖ Disabling intensity

The probability of migraine is 92 percent in patients who report at least four of the five POUND symptoms. The probability decreases to 64 percent in patients with three of the symptoms, and 17 percent in patients with two or less symptoms ⁽⁷⁾.

Treatment of Migraine

Treating acute migraine is challenging because of substantial rates of nonresponse to medications and difficulty in predicting individual response to a specific agent or dose ⁽⁸⁾. Migraine's pharmacotherapy has two goals: stopping the acute attack and preventing subsequent attack ⁽⁹⁾. Migraine headache treated by nasal route with or without using drug medications

Non-Drug Treatments (Supportive & Lifestyle)

- Regular sleep, meals, and hydration
- Stress reduction (yoga, meditation, cognitive-behavioral therapy)
- Avoiding known triggers
- Biofeedback therapy
- Acupuncture (for some patients)

Drug treatments

The nasal route is a fast and effective way to treat migraines, especially when oral medications are not suitable (e.g., due to nausea or vomiting). Here's a list of main nasal treatments currently used:

1. Triptan Nasal Sprays

These are first-line drugs for moderate to severe migraine attacks

Table no3.1: Triptan nasal spray

Drug	Brand Name	Dose	Onset	Notes
Sumatriptan	Imitrex, Migranow	5, 10, or 20 mg	~15–30 min	Works quickly; commonly used; may cause a bitter taste
Zolmitriptan	Zomig	2.5 mg, 5 mg	~15 min	Fast-acting; well tolerated

Triptans

Triptans are a migraine-specific medication line. They are appropriate as first-line therapy for patients with moderate to severe migraine ⁽¹⁰⁾. Triptans are selective 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) receptor agonists which are prescribed to manage acute migraine headaches by disruption of peripheral and central Trigemino-vascular neuronal communication ⁽¹¹⁾. The migraine-specific ‘triptans’ have revolutionized the treatment of migraine ⁽¹²⁾.

Some of the triptans are,

- Sumatriptan
- Zolmitriptan
- Rizatriptan
- Naratriptan
- Almotriptan
- Frovatriptan
- Eletriptan

Sumatriptan

Sumatriptan was the first triptan approved (1997) by the FDA for nasal use and is currently available both as nasal spray solution (Imitrex®/ Imig ran®) and nasal powder (Onzetra Xsail). Sumatriptan is the most widely prescribed triptan for migraine ⁽¹³⁾. Sumatriptan, a

Selective agonist of serotonin receptors 5-HT_{1B} and 5-HT_{1D}. It is used to alleviate migraine and cluster headaches. Sumatriptan nasal powder delivered by the Breath-Powered⁽¹⁴⁾. AVP-825 consists of a breath-powered exhalation device and a low-dose dry powder formulation of sumatriptan (22 mg), supplied as a reusable mouthpiece and two disposable nosepieces each containing a capsule filled with 11 mg sumatriptan nasal powder⁽¹⁵⁾. A significant number of individuals with migraines experience nausea and vomiting, rendering oral treatments ineffective. Although sumatriptan has been detected in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) following intravenous (IV) infusion, its transport across the blood–brain barrier (BBB) remains limited. Delivering hydrophilic drugs to the brain continues to pose challenges in treating central nervous system (CNS)-related disorders. To address these limitations, intranasal (IN) administration has been extensively studied as a practical and noninvasive alternative for drug delivery to the brain. IN-administered drugs can bypass the BBB, offering targeted brain delivery. However, one drawback of IN instillation of solutions is their low residence time in the nasal cavity, approximately 15 minutes. Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs), the second generation of lipid nanoparticles, have been developed to enhance mucosal adhesion and prolong retention time in the nasal cavity. These carriers also improve solubilization capacity, entrapment efficiency, and permeability by bypassing efflux transporters. Studies have shown that sumatriptan-loaded NLCs administered intranasally exhibit high drug targeting efficiency and direct transport to the brain, making them a promising approach for effective migraine treatment⁽¹¹⁾. AVP-825 effectively deposits sumatriptan powder into the regions of the nasal mucosa where it adheres to ciliated epithelium that is more vascular and hence able to absorb powder sumatriptan more readily than liquid sumatriptan delivered via traditional nasal spray⁽¹⁶⁾.

Mechanism of sumatriptan

- Vasoconstriction of Cranial Blood Vessels
- Inhibition of Neurogenic Inflammation
- Direct Action on Trigeminal Nerve Terminals

Fig no 3.1: Mechanism of sumatriptan

Side effects of sumatriptan

- Irritation of burning in your nose or throat after using this nasal spray (sometimes nosebleeds)
- Bad taste in mouth
- Abdominal or stomach pain
- Changes in patterns and rhythm of speech
- Anxiety
- Feeling sick (nausea or vomiting)

Zolmitriptan (2003)

Zolmitriptan is a potent second-generation triptan prescribed for patients with migraine attacks, with or without an aura, and cluster headaches. It has a very effective in reducing migraine symptoms, including pain, nausea and photo- or phonophobia. But its low bioavailability often requires repeated doses, which can lead to side effects. To enhance its effectiveness, zolmitriptan was incorporated into a liposome-based intranasal gel. The formulation was optimized using a Central Composite Design with a response surface methodology. Zolmitriptan Liposomal gel has better efficacy, good tolerability, and enhanced bioavailability, making it an optimal treatment for acute Migraine. zolmitriptan microemulsion used for intranasal application. Submicron emulsion was a relatively safe formulation for nasal administration, submicron emulsion as a new drug carrier for nasal delivery of ZT⁽¹⁷⁾. The potential of novel nanovesicular fatty acid enriched structures

(novasomes) for effective and enhanced nasal delivery of zolmitriptan and investigate their nose to brain targeting potential. Novasomes were prepared using non-ionic surfactant, cholesterol in addition to a free fatty acid. Novasomes are non-phospholipid, vesicular systems that are structurally similar to liposomes but with enhanced stability and loading capacity ⁽¹⁸⁾. Zolmitriptan (ZT) loaded transferosome formulation using Box-Behnken design for improving the bioavailability by nasal route for quick relief of migraine and further to compare with a marketed nasal spray ⁽¹⁹⁾.

Mechanism of zolmitriptan

The drug can be absorbed into the systemic circulation and reach the brain by crossing the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Additionally, it may be transported directly from the nasal cavity to the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and brain tissue via the olfactory and trigeminal neural pathways.

- Activation of 5-HT_{1B} and 5-HT_{1D} Receptors
- Vasoconstriction of Dilated Cranial Blood Vessels
- Inhibition of Neurogenic Inflammation
- Inhibition of Pain Signal Transmission

Side effects of zolmitriptan

- Tingling or warm sensations
- Dry mouth
- Heaviness or tightness in the chest, throat, or jaw (usually non-cardiac)
- Nausea or vomiting
- Chest pain or pressure
- Shortness of breath
- Irregular heartbeat
- Heart attack
- Allergic reaction

2. CGRP Antagonist Nasal Spray (New Class)

It works by blocking the activity of calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP), a molecule involved in the transmission of pain and dilation of blood vessels during a migraine. These are non-vasoconstrictive, so they are safer for patients with heart disease.

Derivatives of CGRP antagonists

- Rimegepant
- Ubrogepant
- Zavegepant
- Atogepant
- Telcagepant
- MK-3207

Table no3.2: CGRP Antagonist Nasal Spray

Drug	Brand Name	Dose	Onset	Notes
Zavegepant	Zavzpret (Pfizer)	10 mg	~15–30 min	FDA-approved in 2023; suitable for patients who cannot take triptans

Zavegepant

Zavegepant is a third-generation CGRP receptor antagonist that is small in size and highly soluble. Due to its pharmacological properties, it can be administered intranasally. Zavegepant, sold under the brand name Zavzpret, is a medication used for the acute treatment of migraine in adults. It's a nasal spray that delivers a small molecule CGRP receptor antagonist directly into the nasal passages (It is administered as a single nasal spray, and the recommended dose is 10mg). CGRP is released from sensory nerves and acts as a strong vasodilator.

Mechanism of Zavegepant

1. Zavegepant inhibits the binding of CGRP by binding to the CGRP receptor.
2. The inhibition of the CGRP complex then prevents the activation of the adenylate cyclase pathway.
3. The function of the adenylate cyclase pathway is inhibited preventing vasodilation.

Fig no:3.3 Mechanism of Zavegepant

Side effects of Zavegepant

- Throat and nasal irritation
- Nausea
- Swelling of face or lips
- Breathing difficulty
- Rashes
- Dizziness
- Fatigue

3. Ergotamine Derivatives (Less Common)

Ergotamine is a vasoconstrictor drug historically used for the acute treatment of migraine attacks. It belongs to the ergot alkaloid class and was one of the earliest effective migraine therapies, though it's used far less frequently today due to the development of safer and more specific drugs like triptans and CGRP antagonists.

Ergotamine derivatives used to treat migraine

- Dihydroergotamine (DHE)
- Methysergide
- Lisuride

Dihydroergotamine (DHE)

Table no3.3: Ergotamine Derivatives

Drug	Brand Name	Dose	Onset	Notes
Dihydroergotamine (DHE)	Migranal	0.5 mg per spray	~30 min	Can cause nasal irritation; older option

Dihydroergotamine (DHE) has been available for treating migraine in the United States since 1946. DHE is an ergot derivative that has been extensively utilized and studied in the treatment of episodic and chronic migraine ⁽²⁰⁾. DHE binds with high affinity to serotonin 5-HT_{1D} α and 5-HT_{1D} β receptors as well as 5-HT 1A, 5-HT 2A, and 5-HT 2C receptors, noradrenaline α _{2A}, α _{2B}, and α ₁ receptors, and dopamine D_{2L} and D₃ receptors. DHE has a considerably longer dissociation half-life compared to sumatriptan. The mechanism of action is most likely vasoconstriction by stimulating α -adrenergic and 5-HT receptors. DHE delivered by a traditional nasal spray pump (Migranal) has been available in the United States since gaining US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval in August 1997.¹⁸ However, the bioavailability of the nasal spray is variable and low, at only approximately 32% of the injectable formulation, with a delayed peak plasma concentration and slow onset of action ⁽²¹⁾. DHE are reached 30 to 60 minutes after administration, as compared with 1 to 2 minutes following intravenous administration of DHE and 24 minutes after intramuscular ⁽²²⁾.

Mechanism of dihydroergotamine (DHE)

- It binds to noradrenaline and dopamine receptors.
- It stimulates vasoconstriction by stimulating alpha-adrenergic and serotonin receptor.
- It has high affinity for 5-HT 1,2 receptors.
- Activation of 5HT₁-Vasoconstriction-Migraine relief.

Side effects of Dihydroergotamine

- Nausea and vomiting
- Nasal irritation
- Diarrhea or abdominal discomfort
- Muscle pain or weakness
- Metallic taste (nasal spray)

SUMMARY

Migraine is the third most common disease worldwide characterized by current episodes of severe headaches. Migraine long lasting from 4 to 72 hours if untreated. It is more common to women than to men. The generation of pain in migraine attack is related to the neurogenic inflammation, production of neuropeptide, and activation of meningeal afferents. Migraine's pharmacotherapy has two goals: stopping the acute attack and preventing subsequent attack. Migraine headache treated by nasal route with or without using drug medications. Non drug treatments such as Regular sleep, meals, and hydration, Stress reduction (yoga, meditation, cognitive-behavioral therapy), Avoiding known triggers. Some of the effective drug treatments are Triptans (sumatriptan, zolmitriptan, Rizatriptan, Almotriptan, etc...), calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) antagonist (Zavegepant, Rimegepant, Atogepant, etc...), Ergotamine Derivatives (Dihydroergotamine, Methysergide, Lisuride). Intranasal drug delivery enables dose reduction, rapid attainment of therapeutic blood levels, quicker onset of pharmacological activity, and fewer side effects. The mucociliary clearance system in the nasal cavity works to rapidly remove foreign substances, which can limit the effectiveness of nasal drug delivery. Absorption enhancers work by boosting the rate at which a drug crosses the nasal mucosa.

CONCLUSION

Recently, nasal drug delivery has been exploited for the systemic delivery of low molecular weight polar drugs, peptides and proteins which are not easily administered by any other routes except injection or when there is a need for rapid action. Treating acute migraine is challenging because of substantial rates of nonresponse to medications and difficulty in predicting individual response to a specific agent or dose. Intranasal route are more effective as compared to other routes. Intranasal drug delivery system shows excellent

bioavailability for low molecular weight drugs and side effects are reduced due to low dose. High molecular weight substance cannot be delivered through this nasal route.

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